

FAILURE LOCUS ANALYSIS OF FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES UNDER COMBINED TRANSVERSE STRESSES THROUGH COMPUTATIONAL MICROMECHANICS

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ABSTRACT

The failure locus of unidirectional fibre-reinforced composites subjected to combined transverse stresses, whose experimental tests are highly complex, is studied using computational micromechanics. A representative volume element (RVE) of a lamina microstructure with a 60% volume fraction of random distribution fibres is generated. The RVE model explicitly takes into account the fibres, matrix, and interfaces between fibres and matrix. The Drucker-Prager model and cohesive zone model are used to simulate matrix plastic deformation and interfacial debonding respectively. Progressive failure procedure for both the matrix and interface is considered during the simulation. The transverse strengths are obtained by the finite element method under periodic boundary conditions through a uniaxial load. The micro failure of simulation results reveals that tensile failure of interface firstly occurs at the equators of interfaces under transverse tension. Shear failure of interface firstly occurs at the $\pm 45^\circ$ locations of the interfaces under transverse compression. The tensile and shear failures of interface occur simultaneously at the $+45^\circ$ locations of the interfaces under shear. The various loading conditions are then loaded to the microstructure model in combined stress states using different force ratios to obtain the failure locus of microstructures. The corresponding failure loci are compared with the Hashin criteria whose strength properties are obtained from the numerical results. Then a modified Hashin criterion is proposed through inducing a first-order item into the transverse tensile criterion whose failure surface is smoother at the piecewise points than Hashin criterion. We concluded that the numerical results are more coincident with the modified Hashin criteria.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composites show outstanding specific stiffness and strength and this leads to a wide range of applications as structural materials. Unlike conventional materials, these composites cannot be equivalent to simple homogeneous and isotropic materials. For instance, a composite lamina presents different failure mechanisms depending on the loading modes. Longitudinal tension leads to fibre fracture while compression induces localized fibre buckling. Transverse tension results in matrix cracking, and transverse compression triggers fracture by the formation of matrix shear bands. The shear loads in longitudinal or transverse direction may also lead to the matrix failure. Moreover, the different failure mechanisms are interacted with each other. As the above mentioned content, the failure criteria for fibre reinforced composites should be constructed accurately and reliably using mechanical properties.

The World Wide Failure Exercise [1-3] compared the differences between nineteen failure criteria which were proposed by different researchers in recent years. Within the nineteen failure criteria, Hashin [4, 5] used different failure equations as a function of the dominant stress state due to the coexistence of various physical mechanisms of failure in fibre reinforced composites. He distinguished the fibre and matrix dominated failure, and each one was subdivided into tensile and compressive modes. It has been demonstrated that the Hashin failure criteria in 12 stress plane are very good agreement with the off-axis test experimental data of a unidirectional lamina [5]. However, the out-of-plane properties of composites are also very important when a laminate plate is subjected to a local

low-velocity impact load. Hashin proposed a failure criterion in 23 stress plane which can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{Y_T^2}(\sigma_2 + \sigma_3)^2 + \frac{1}{S_T^2}(\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_2\sigma_3) = 1, & \sigma_2 + \sigma_3 > 0 \\ \frac{1}{Y_C} \left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_T} \right)^2 - 1 \right] (\sigma_2 + \sigma_3) + \frac{1}{4S_T^2} (\sigma_2 + \sigma_3)^2 + \frac{1}{S_T^2} (\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_2\sigma_3) = 1, & \sigma_2 + \sigma_3 < 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where Y_T , Y_C , and S_T stand for the transverse tension, compression and shear strength, respectively. It is notoriously difficult to verify the validity of this failure criterion through using the experimental method due to the complexity of test clamp. Moreover, the experimental data often present scatter and this approach is expensive and time consuming.

The computational micromechanical method has been validated as an effective tool to determine the mechanical behaviour of a composite lamina. This method explicitly takes into account the fibres, matrix and interfaces in a lamina basing on the numerical simulation of a representative volume element of the composite microstructure [6-11]. Romanowicz [12] has indicated that local fibre array irregularities are a significant contributor to matrix cracking through local stress concentrations and the occurrence of localization. Vaughan [13] compared the influence of weak and strong interface on the thermal residual stress. Yang et al. [14] have concluded that the tension fracture initiates as interfacial debonding and evolves as a result of interactions between interfacial debonding and matrix plastic deformation, while the compression failure is dominated by matrix plastic damage. Melro et al. [15] have studied the influence of interface and epoxy matrix on the strength properties of composite, damage initiation and propagation under different loading conditions. González and co-workers [16-18] have investigated the failure behaviour of fibre-reinforced composites and obtained the failure loci of composites under combined transverse compression and out-of-plane shear. They concluded that the estimations of the failure criteria were largely consistent with the numerical simulations in the composites with a strong interface but overestimated the composite strength when the interface was weak. But they didn't study the failure loci of composites under transverse tension.

In our investigation, the computational micromechanics are used to simulate the transverse failure locus of a fibre reinforced composite lamina. The stress-strain curves and micromechanical failures of microstructure models are studied under transverse tension, compression, and shear. Then the microstructure is subjected to combined transverse stress state under periodic boundary conditions to obtain the failure locus of microstructures. At last we compared the numerical results with the Hashin criterion and the modified Hashin criterion which is smoother at the piecewise points than Hashin criterion through inducing a first-order item into the transverse tensile criterion.

2 COMPUTATIONAL MECHANICAL MODEL

2.1 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

In order to study the micromechanics of the fibre-reinforced composites, a representative volume element (RVE) of the microstructure should be constructed firstly. In our investigation, six different fibre random distributions are generated with a 60% volume fraction of fibres to study the numerical dispersion, as shown in Fig. 1. Each RVE model contains 25 fibres of a $5\mu\text{m}$ radius in an $L \times L$ square. The fibre positions within the RVE model keep a periodic condition through splitting the edge fibres into two parts and pasting the out-of-zone part to the opposite sides of the RVE model. The interface is embedded between each fibre and matrix. ABAQUS/Explicit is used to generate the RVE model and do the numerical analysis. The fibres and matrix are meshed with 4-node bilinear plane strain reduced integration elements (CPE4R) mainly and a few 3-node triangle elements (CPE3). The interface between fibres and matrix is meshed with 4-node two-dimensional cohesive elements (COH2D4).

2.2 Material properties of fiber, matrix, and interface

Since the fibre failure will not occur under transverse stress state, the reinforcing fibres are assumed to present a linear elastic isotropic constitutive behaviour. The Young's Modulus and

Poisson's ratio are set as 40GPa and 0.25, respectively.

Figure 1: Six RVE models and relevant meshes.

The matrix is assumed to behave as an elastic-plastic solid. The elastic properties for the matrix are $E_m=4\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_m=0.35$. Furthermore, the progressive damage and failure behaviour are considered for the onset of matrix damage prediction. Since polymeric matrix exhibits an internal friction phenomenon, plastic deformation can be modelled with the Mohr-Coulomb or Drucker-Prager yield criterion. The Drucker-Prager yield surface is more attractive than the Mohr-Coulomb yield surface from the standpoint of numerical implementation, since the yield surface has a continuously varying normal [19]. Moreover, the Drucker-Prager yield criterion can closely approximate the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion through selecting property material parameters. It also provides for a possibly noncircular yield surface in the deviatoric plane to match different yield values in triaxial tension and compression. In this paper, the extended linear Drucker-Prager criterion provided by ABAQUS [20] is employed to the matrix material, which can be expressed as

$$F = t - p \tan \beta - d = 0, t = \frac{1}{2} q \left[1 + \frac{1}{k} - \left(1 - \frac{1}{k} \right) \left(\frac{r}{q} \right)^3 \right] \quad (2)$$

where p is the hydrostatic stress, q is the Mises equivalent stress, r is the third invariant of deviatoric stress, β is the slope of the linear yield surface in the p - t stress plane, d is the cohesion of the material, and k is the ratio of the yield stress in triaxial tension to the yield stress in triaxial compression.

The cohesion, d , of matrix can be defined by the uniaxial compression yield strength, σ_c , or the uniaxial tension yield strength, σ_t . The relationship between d and the yield stresses is expressed as follows:

$$d = \begin{cases} \left(1 - \frac{1}{3} \tan \beta \right) \sigma_c \\ \left(\frac{1}{k} + \frac{1}{3} \tan \beta \right) \sigma_t \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In equation (3), we need to confirm at least three material parameters. The yield stresses, σ_c and σ_t , which can be easily obtained by the experimental tests, are set as 101.9MPa and 60MPa according to Ref. [16], respectively. But the slope, β , of the linear yield surface cannot be directly available by experiments. Instead, it can be defined from the friction angle, ϕ , of the Mohr-Coulomb model in the case of plain strain by [20]:

$$\tan \beta = \frac{3 \sin \phi}{\sqrt{3 + \sin^2 \phi}} \quad (4)$$

The friction angle is often set as 15° , so the slope degree can be calculated as 24° . Using the Mohr-Coulomb model, we can obtain the value of angle between the fracture plane and the direction perpendicular to the loading axis, which is related to the friction angle ϕ by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tension:} \quad & \alpha = 45^\circ - \phi / 2 \\ \text{Compression:} \quad & \alpha = 45^\circ + \phi / 2 \\ \text{Shear:} \quad & \alpha = \pm \phi / 2 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

After the onset of failure, a progressive failure procedure controls the damage evolution. The fracture energy G_f per unit area is given as a small value of 0.5J/m^2 to satisfy the final brittle failure no matter under uniaxial tension or compression.

Finally, cohesive zone model is used to simulate the interface between fibre and matrix. The mechanical behaviour of interface model is expressed in terms of a bi-linear traction-separation law which relates the displacement between top and bottom faces of cohesive element with the traction vector acting upon it. Initial stiffness of the cohesive element is set to 108MPa/mm to maintain the continuity of stress and strain fields between fibre and matrix. The strength of interface is determined by the normal and tangential interfacial strengths which for simplicity are assumed to be equal to 39.1MPa according to Ref. [16]. The maximum stress criterion is used to dictate the onset of damage. The rate of damage progression is controlled by the fracture energy which is set as 100J/m^2 .

2.3 Boundary conditions and loading methods

Periodic boundary conditions are applied to the edges of the RVEs to ensure consistent deformation of the opposite edges. Equations for establishing periodic boundary conditions are expressed as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_E - \mathbf{u}_{ES} &= \mathbf{u}_W - \mathbf{u}_{WS} \\ \mathbf{u}_N - \mathbf{u}_{NW} &= \mathbf{u}_S - \mathbf{u}_{SW} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{u} represents the any displacement vector on the boundary, and $N, S, W,$ and E subscripts refer to the north, south, west, and east edges, while subscripts with two letters, correspond to the vertexes of the RVE, as shown in Fig. 2. The west-south vertex is constrained as well as the east-south vertex is suppressed in the vertical direction to prevent rigid body motions.

The horizontal force and the vertical force are respectively applied incrementally to the east-south vertex and the west-north vertex for studying the (σ_2, σ_3) stress plane locus as shown in Fig. 2a. For the (σ_2, σ_{23}) stress state, the horizontal forces are both applied to the two vertexes as shown in Fig. 2b.

Figure 2: Periodic boundary conditions and different loading methods.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Micromechanical failure

For each loading condition, the homogenized stress-strain curves up to failure of RVE models are exported using the ABAQUS post-process. The stress-strain curves are obtained after performing volumetric homogenization expressed as follow

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{N_p} \sigma_{ij}^k V^k}{\sum_{k=1}^{N_p} V^k} \quad (7)$$

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{N_p} \varepsilon_{ij}^k V^k}{\sum_{k=1}^{N_p} V^k}$$

where σ_{ij} and ε_{ij} are the homogenized stress and strain components, σ_{ij}^k and ε_{ij}^k are the stress and strain components at integration point k , V^k is the associated volume at integration point k , N_p represents the total number of integration points in the RVE (Because the interface only play the role of connection fibre and matrix, the cohesive elements are not involved in equation (7)).

Fig. 3 shows the stress-strain curves of RVE models under transverse compression, tension, and pure shear. The absolute values of the stress and strain are used to plot the curves in compression. As can be seen from the figure, for the transverse tension and shear, all the curves are almost superposed, and only a few divergences occur after the onset of damage. For the transverse compression, a few divergences occur after the plastic deformation stage of the RVE model. The failure strength of each model also presents some scatters. But the dispersion of data keeps within 8%. This indicates that our random fibre distribution models could be used to predict the transverse strengths and study the failure locus correctly.

The non-linearity of the curves indicates that the plastic properties of the matrix. After the brittle fracture occurs in the RVE model under compression and tension, the homogenized stress will be suddenly reduced. Therefore, when the fracture occurs, the RVE model could not bear the increasing external loads which achieve the value of the material strength. The homogenized stress at this moment is set as the strength of the material. The compression strength (125MPa) is larger than the tension strength (55MPa). This phenomenon conforms to the most fibre reinforced polymer lamina. Compared with tensile and compressive curves, the shear stress-strain curves are more plat at the strength value which presents a plastic-perfectly state. The failure strain of shear is about 0.017 which is bigger than that of tension (0.006) and compression (0.012).

Figure 3: Stress-strain curves of RVE models under transverse compression, tension, and shear

Due to the similar damage localization pattern of all six models, only Model 1 is presented. Fig. 4 shows the final damage of Model 1 under transverse tension, compression, and shear conditions respectively. Under transverse tension, the tensile damage of interface first occurs at the equators of the interfaces. Then the fracture failure will expand gradually to the two poles along the circular interface. Finally, interfacial debonding at neighbour locations is linked throughout the RVE model by matrix cracks which are perpendicular to the loading direction. Affected by the random distribution of fibre, fracture extended direction is a twist line bypassing fibres through the whole model. Under compression, the shear damage of interface first occurs at the $\pm 45^\circ$ locations of the interfaces. Then the crack extends along about 52.5° direction in the matrix. The expanding direction is coincided with the Mohr-Coulomb plastic flow direction and this verifies that the accurateness of our numerical

micromechanical model. Under shear status, both the tensile and shear damage occur simultaneously at the $+45^\circ$ locations of the interfaces and then the fracture direction is 7.5° along the vertical or horizontal direction in the matrix as shown in Fig. 4c.

From above discussion and combined with equation (5), we can conclude that the fracture direction would not change under transverse compression and shear after the introduction of random fibres and interfaces, while the crack angle will change from 37.5° to vertical direction of the load direction under transverse tension after the introduction of random fibres and interfaces.

Figure 4: Micromechanical failures of RVE model under transverse compression, tension, and shear

3.2 Failure locus under combined transverse stresses

In order to compare the failure locus predicted by the numerical model with the Hashin failure criteria, the various loading conditions are loaded to the RVE model in combined stress states using different force ratios at the vertexes of the model. As shown in Fig. 5 and 6, we set the force ratio ($f_3:f_2$ and $f_{23}:f_2$ in Fig. 2) as a wanted value and then the homogenized stresses are recorded during loading increments. As can be seen in the figures, before the fracture occurrence points, the failure loci are almost linear along the stress ratios. When a fracture occurs, the locus curves reach their inflexional points and these mean that the RVE model could not bear the increasing external loads anymore. Shown in the third quadrant of Fig. 5, we can conclude that the RVE model could not failure under a biaxial compressive loading condition with a $-1:-1$ ratio of $f_2:f_3$. This is coincided with the Mohr-Coulomb model. The failure loci are symmetrical along the 45° direction under the combined biaxial normal stresses (Fig. 5) while symmetrical along the horizontal direction under the combined normal and shear stresses (Fig. 6).

Figure 5: Mechanical response of RVE model under combined transverse normal stresses

Figure 6: Mechanical response of RVE model under combined transverse normal and shear stresses

3.3 Failure surface

The numerical results of the fracture occurrence points are shown in Fig. 7 and 8. For comparison, the Hashin criteria (equation (1)) are also plotted in the figures. The strengths in equation (1) are calculated by the maximum stresses during transverse tension, compression, and shear according to Section 3.1. As can be seen in the figures, the numerical results are almost superposed with the Hashin failure criterion under compressive condition. However, under tensile loading, some differences exist between the simulations and the Hashin criteria. We can see that the Hashin criteria are underestimated for biaxial tensions and overestimated under combined tensile and shear stresses.

Figure 7: Failure surface of RVE model under combined transverse normal stresses

In order to precisely predict the microstructure failure of fibre reinforced composite lamina, we develop a modified criterion based on the Hashin criteria (equation (1)):

$$\frac{\text{sgn}(\sigma_2 + \sigma_3)}{Y} \left[1 - \left(\frac{Y}{2S_T} \right)^2 \right] (\sigma_2 + \sigma_3) + \frac{1}{4S_T^2} (\sigma_2 + \sigma_3)^2 + \frac{1}{S_T^2} (\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_2 \sigma_3) = 1. \quad (8)$$

In equation (8), $Y=Y_T$ when $\sigma_2+\sigma_3>0$, and $Y=Y_C$ otherwise. Compared the equation (8) with (1), we can see that the expressions are the same when $\sigma_2+\sigma_3<0$. For the case of $\sigma_2+\sigma_3>0$, a first-order item is introduced into the transverse tensile criterion for the modified Hashin criterion which is just like the transverse compressive criterion. Then we can see that the modified criteria are smoother than Hashin criteria at the piecewise points ($\sigma_2+\sigma_3=0$) in Fig. 7 and 8. Furthermore, the numerical results are more coincident with the modified Hashin criteria.

Figure 8: Failure surface of RVE model under combined transverse normal and shear stresses

4 CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical behavior of a fibre-reinforced composite lamina under transverse stresses has been simulated using computational micromechanics. The transverse tensile, compressive, and shear strengths of the lamina are obtained through the stress-strain curves. The various loading conditions are loaded to the RVE model under combined stress states using different force ratios to obtain the failure locus of microstructures. Then we compare the numerical failure locus with the Hashin criteria and the modified Hashin criteria. The modified Hashin criterion is smoother at the piecewise points than Hashin criterion through inducing a first-order item into the transverse tensile criterion. We concluded that the numerical results are more coincident with the modified Hashin criteria.

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